

Open Smart Virtual Class Room: Extensible and Scalable Learning System in Smart Space

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ABSTRACT

E-LEARNING, as a significant modern education and learning approach and tool, is defined as learning activities performed over electronic devices. Virtual universities are becoming strongly networked and fundamental changes in the organization of education are occurring. We are going to give the real time interactive virtual classroom with tele education experience, which is an important approach in distance learning. However, most current systems fail to meet new challenges in extensibility and scalability, which mainly lie with three issues. First, open system architecture is required to better support the integration of increasing human-computer interfaces and personal mobile devices in the classroom. Second, the learning system should facilitate opening its interfaces, which will help easy deployment that copes with different circumstances and allows other learning systems to talk to each other. Third, problems emerge on binding existing systems of classrooms together in different places or even different countries such as tackling systems intercommunication and distant intercultural learning in different languages. To address these issues, we build an application called Open Smart Classroom built on our software infrastructure based on the multivalent system architecture using Web Service technology in Smart Space.

Keywords: Pervasive computing, computer uses in education, Web-based services

1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the new generation of Web based learning systems, traditional learning mode, where teachers and students are face to face with each other in the same classroom continues to have its unrivaled advantages. Unlike many Web-based learning systems adopting a synchronized way here, the teacher publishes learning content statically on the Internet and students obtain static learning materials at different times, real classroom learning follows a synchronized learning process, where students in and out of classroom can listen to the live instruction while the teacher gives the lectures.

In most cases, synchronized learning catches participants' attention and interest much more effectively than synchronized one. Therefore, real-

time interactive virtual classroom with tele-education experience is of indispensable significance in distance learning. Further, with the development of pervasive computing aimed at providing natural human-computer interface and multimodality communications, integrating pervasive computing facilitate the teacher to teach the class and help the students learn and discuss with others.

Several projects, such as and implement special human-computing interfaces in their learning environment. At the same time, mobile devices such as mobile phone, smart phone, PDA, and laptop have been easily accessible for ordinary people. The teacher easily interacts with local and remote students while the students are able to give feedback to the teacher.

2. EXISTING SYSTEM

Systems of classrooms together in different places or even different countries such as tackling systems intercommunication and distant intercultural learning in different languages. Scalability problem is large in user interact with server.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We build a prototype application called Open Smart Classroom built on us software infrastructure based on the multivalent system architecture using Web Service technology in Smart Space. A learning environment integrated by pervasive computing technologies, the classroom-based e-learning system could be considered as a Smart Space, which benefits the existing solutions of Smart Space.

Figure 1. Open Smart Platform runtime architecture for single Smart Space

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

Role-based Authorization: The role-based access control (RBAC) is a flexible approach that has generated great interest in the security community. RBAC has emerged as a widely accepted alternative to classical discretionary and mandatory access controls. Several models of RBAC have been published and several commercial implementations are available. RBAC regulates the access of users to information and system resources on the basis of activities that users need to execute in the system. It requires the identification of roles in the system. A role can be defined as a set of actions and responsibilities associate with a particular working activity. Then,

instead of specifying all the accesses each individual user is allowed, access authorizations on objects are specified for roles. Since roles in an organization are relatively persistent with respect to user turnover and task re-assignment, RBAC provides a powerful mechanism for reducing the complexity, cost, and potential for error in assigning permissions to users within the organization. Because roles within an organization typically have overlapping permissions RBAC models include features to establish role hierarchies, where a given role can include all of the permissions of another role. Another fundamental aspect of RBAC is authorization constraints (also simply called constraints). A user is a human being or an autonomous agent, a role

is a job function or a job title within the organization with some associated semantics regarding the authority and responsibility conferred on a member of the role, and a permission is an approval of a particular mode of access to one or more objects in the system or some privilege to carry out specified actions. Roles are organized in a partial order ³, so that if $x \succ y$ then role x inherits the permissions of role y . Members of x are also implicitly members of y . In such cases, we say x is senior to y . Each session relates one user to possibly many roles.

A user can be a member of many roles and a role can have many users. Similarly, a role can have much permission and the same permissions can be assigned to many roles. Each session relates one user to possibly many roles. Intuitively, a user establishes a session during which the user activates some subset of roles that he or she is a member of. The permissions available to the users are the union of permissions from all roles activated in that session. Each session is associated with a single user. This association remains constant for the life of a session. A user may have multiple sessions open at the same time, each in a different window on the workstation screen for instance. Each session may have a different combination of active roles. The concept of a session equates to the traditional notation of a subject in access control. A subject is a unit of access control, and a user may have multiple subjects (or sessions) with different permissions active at the same time. There is a collection of constraints that allow or forbid values of various components of the RBAC model.

Work that is directly related to delegation

Gasser and McDermott defined user to machine delegation as “the process whereby a user in a distributed environment authorizes a system to access remote resources on his behalf.” The user’s authorization of his process to act on his behalf is a form of delegation of rights from the user to the process. In some cases, the user may delegate the rights to one of several permissible roles or identities (e.g., by logging in using different names and/or passwords), in order to limit the actions of the process to some subset that user is authorized. Limited delegation also occurs

routinely in multilevel secure systems where the user selects a single classification of his process that is a subset of the access class for which the user is authorized.

RBAC-Flat Roles: A user is a human being, a role is a job function and permission is an approval of access to some objects or a privilege to carry out a particular task. The management of permissions and roles is greatly simplified by associating permissions with the roles and assigning the users to roles. In this way the users acquire the associated permission. Roles are created for various job functions in an organization. The permissions required to carry out the jobs are associated with the roles. New permissions can be granted to roles as new applications and systems are incorporated. Unnecessary permissions can be revoked from the roles. Users are assigned to the roles depending on the responsibilities and qualifications and can be reassigned from one role to another.

RBDM0-Flat roles: The delegation addressed in this model is a one step delegation. This means that the delegated role cannot be further delegated. Hence, only the original members can delegate. We will keep this assumption in our original model, but as part of our extended model we will relax this assumption and extend the model to allow some multi-step delegation. The delegation is total. Each user in a delegating role delegates the total package of permissions embodied in that role or does not delegate at all.

Revocation using time out

In using this approach, we attach a time clock to every assigned delegation so that when the assigned time expires, the delegation also expires.

Using timeouts has the following advantages:

- Timeout revocation is a simple self triggering process that ensures the revocation of delegate membership automatically.
- In attaching a timeout to the delegation we no longer have to worry about tracking the sponsoring roles (the delegator).

Using timeouts has the following disadvantages:

- Timeouts by themselves are not enough to ensure security.
- If there is no other tracking mechanism, delegate members can behave in a bad manner during the duration of the time set which can cause great harm to the system before revocation takes place by time out.
- When employing this approach, we have to choose the time carefully, because we might overset or under set the time for delegate members.

Management Login: The Valid user (Professor, Lecturer, Staff) enter into login to send data or information to any person in the virtual university (collaboration of 3 universities).

In this Module each and every one will have own user id and password to log in.

Using their Id they can login to any other university which is in collaboration with virtual universities. The information about particular professor or lecturer is displayed in their login; apart from that they have three responsibilities of delegation, revocation of roles and uploading new software's and materials.

Students Login: Students enter into login to download any subject materials by their provided student Id and they can ask any queries related to subjects to any staff working in the virtual university.

Role Delegation: The Member of the virtual university can delegate his/her role and also bellowed role to other member in virtual university.

Role Revocation: The Member of the virtual university can revoke his/her role for which he/she already delegated or assigned role to other member in virtual university.

Upload and Download Materials: Both students and members of the management can upload and download the subject materials needed but the

only thing is student cant able to delete any files in Storage and also there is no need of this work for students.

5. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS:

The future work includes two parts.

- 1) One is to analyze constraints in the delegation model at a virtual university
- 2) We have mentioned the time temporal duration as a constraint in our delegation model, but it needs more work on constraints including the constraints in the GTRBAC model.

6. CONCLUSION

A delegating framework including delegating authorization and revocation with constraints as a single and extended it to include group-based Delegation through Role Based Access Control Management (RBAC). Finally, the proposed role-based delegation framework in this paper is demonstrated by its implementation with XML.

REFERENCES

- 1) M. Abadi, M. Burrows, B. Lampson, and G. Plotkin, "A Calculus for Access Control in Distributed Systems," ACM Trans. Programming Languages and Systems, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 706-734, 1993.
- 2) G. Ahn, B. Mohan, and S. Hong, "Towards Secure Information Sharing Using Role-Based Delegation," J. Network and Computer Applications, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 42-59, 2007.
- 3) G. Ahn and R. Sandhu, "Role-Based Authorization Constraints Specification," Information and System Security, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 207-226, 2000.
- 4) G. Ahn and R. Sandhu, "Decentralized User Group Assignment in Windows NT," J. Systems and Software, vol. 56, no. 1, pp. 39-49, 2001.
- 5) M. Arenas and L. Libkin, "A Normal Form for XML Documents," ACM Trans. Database Systems, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 195-232, 2004.